

Biomimetics in wind turbine blade designs: a review from aerodynamic perspective

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Abstract: To meet rapid energy demand, clean energy sources like wind have the potential to play a vital role. In context of Bangladesh with its low wind speed to produce maximum power from wind turbines various modifications are needed. The aim of this research is to provide a comparative analysis among different nature inspired modifications of wind turbine blades and find out the best possible biomimetic approach to enhance the performance of wind turbines in low wind-speed regions like Bangladesh. Through implementing diverse biomimetic approaches, such as, humpback whale tubercles in fin, bird wings, penguin flippers, and butterfly wings into blade design will not only increase the power output but also lower the cut-in speed. Literature reveals that horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWT) inspired by albatross and stork wings have potential to harness wind energy under low wind speed conditions achieving power coefficient (C_p) 0.440 to 0.445 for albatross wings and 0.384 to .407 for stork wings. From this study, wind turbine inspired by Maple seeds turns out to be the best modification, along with Albatross and Storks wings showing higher power coefficient. This comparative analysis will be beneficial for the researchers to select the best biomimetic modification or best sets of nature inspired modifications for conventional turbines to maximize their performance in low wind-speed regions.

1. Introduction

The global demand for clean energy is rising due to the finite resource of conventional fossil fuels like coal, natural gas, nuclear, and oil. As these non-renewable resources are being rapidly depleted, and at the current rate of consumption, these may last only a few more decades or a century [1]. Renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro, bioenergy, and geothermal offer more sustainable alternatives. Among these, wind energy stands out as one of the most promising solutions for clean power generation. Nature has always been a wellspring of inspiration for engineering innovations, and bio-inspired design also known as biomimicry utilizes nature's wisdom to create solutions to feed human needs [2]. By studying and emulating natural structures, processes, and systems, biomimetics has transformed various fields, including energy, medicine, transportation etc. [3]. In the realm of wind energy, biomimetic blade designs from tubercles of whale fins, bird's primary wing, Fibonacci, and insect flight mechanisms have significantly enhanced aerodynamic performance, reduced drag, lower noise emission, and boosting efficiency [4].

Bangladesh, with its tropical monsoon climate, experiences low to moderate wind speeds. However, coastal microsites like Charfashion and Monpura have shown promising wind speeds of up to 7.3 m/s at 100 m above ground level, making them potential sites for wind energy production [5]. Since wind turbine power output is proportional to the cube of wind speed, optimizing turbine performance is crucial for harnessing maximum energy in low-wind-speed regions [6]. By incorporating biomimetic principles into turbine blade design, wind energy efficiency can be significantly improved, paving the way for a cleaner, more sustainable energy future.

A study investigated that a 3D wind turbine blade modeled after maple seed geometry and analyzed via CFD achieved a power coefficient up to 59%, which is higher than typical wind turbines (C_p : 0.45–0.48) [7]. Another study of Fibonacci-inspired vertical axis wind turbine with logarithmic spiral curvature improved aerodynamic performance achieving a 14.1% higher C_p of 0.391, and a 13.5% higher thrust coefficient ($C_t = 0.391$) [8]. The aerodynamic performance of the wind turbine inspired from the bird species Common Guillemot (*Uria aalge*) was tested in a wind tunnel laboratory and found efficiencies up to 0.3 which is around 53% of the maximum power [9].

To the authors knowledge there is no systematic, up-to-date review of the nature inspired strategies of enhanced wind turbine design based in Bangladesh and the novelty of this work that authors propose an approach to make suitable wind turbine design for Bangladesh. Overall, the objective of this study is to make a comparative review of different biomimetic approaches that will enhance the aerodynamic performance of a wind turbine and to find out the most effective one for wind turbine applications and apply it for Bangladesh wind rich areas.

2. Different Nature Inspired Methods

2.1 Borneo Camphor Seed

The Borneo Camphor seed (*Dryobalanops aromatica*) has pre-coning flexible wings that naturally align with the wind direction. This wing reduces aerodynamic drag. The Borneo camphor seed inspires the design of a flexible-bladed wind turbine. A research study shows that, a flexible-bladed wind turbine (FBWT) inspired from Borneo Camphor seed achieved a power coefficient of 0.0870, while the rigid-bladed wind turbine (RBWT) reached 0.057 [10].

2.2 Maple Seed

The maple seed (*Acer* spp.) has a unique wing that helps to autorotate as soon as it falls from the tree. Researchers developed a wind turbine blade that mimics the rotation of a maple seed. Study found that this design achieved a maximal C_p of 0.284 at a wind speed of 4 m/s [11].

Fig. 1. (a) 3D model of Borneo Camphor seed [12]. (b) 3D model of turbine blade inspired by Fibonacci spiral [13]. (c) 3D model of butterfly wind turbine [14]. (d) Wind turbine blade modeled with sinusoidal leading edge. (e) Wind turbine blade modeled after Maple seed [15].

2.3 Fibonacci Spiral

The Fibonacci spiral is a mathematical pattern where each number is a sum of the previous two numbers. As the pattern progresses, the ratio of consecutive numbers approaches to 1.618, which is a golden ratio, found in nature. Study found that this design increased C_P to 0.391 and improved the thrust coefficient to 0.309, representing a 14.1% and 13.5% enhancement respectively [8].

2.4 Humpback Whale’s Flippers

Humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) has large flippers with bumps on the leading edge. These bumps enhance hydrodynamic performance by increasing the lift and reducing drag. Researchers inspired by the bumpy flippers and implemented leading edge turbines to wind turbines that increase lift coefficient up to 10% [16].

2.5 Butterfly Wing

A butterfly wind turbine (BWT) is a kind of vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) with closed-loop blades, inspired by butterfly wings. These blades form a double-blade structure, which is expected to improve self-starting properties and reduce costs because of their simple construction [17].

2.6 Dragonfly Wing

Dragonfly wings inspire the wind turbine design by their unique aerodynamic efficiency and structural adaptability. The wings of a dragonfly help them to reduce drag and enhance lift. Studies have shown that mimicking dragonfly wings can increase C_P up to 0.35 in HAWT.

3. Recent Research on Different Passive Flow Control Technics

Table 1. provides a detailed overview of biomimetic approaches applied to both Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine (HAWT) and Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT). It highlights nature inspired modifications made to the wind turbine for performance enhancement.

Table 1. Recent research on performance enhancement of wind turbines using nature inspired methods.

Published Year	Biomimicry Method	Turbine Type	Airfoil Type	Modification	Performance After Modification	Reference
2021	Borneo Camphor seed	VAWT	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-coning, flexible, sheetlike blades Passive wind tracking and collapsible blades for extreme wind protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Max C_P: 0.229 at 3 m/s wind speed Fast yaw recovery (90° to 0° in ~1 s) 	[18]
2015	Maple Seed	HAWT	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3D wind turbine blade modeled after maple seed geometry Model analyzed via CFD for aerodynamic potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power Coefficient C_P: 0.59 Maximal C_P: 0.593 (near Betz limit), higher than typical turbines (0.45–0.48) 	[19]
2022	Fibonacci Spiral	VAWT	NACA-0021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fibonacci-inspired blade profile Logarithmic spiral curvature to enhance aerodynamics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average C_P: 0.391 (↑14.1%) Average Thrust Coefficient: 0.309 (↑13.5%) 	[8]

2023	Humpback Whale's Flippers	VAWT	NACA 0021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addition of leading-edge tubercles with varying amplitude and wavelength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-design: C_p degradation of ~ 0.135 ($0.35 \rightarrow 0.30$) Off-design: C_p enhancement of ~ 0.55 ($0.50 \rightarrow 0.78$) 	[20]
2023	Albatross & Stork Wings	HAWT	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airfoils optimized for low wind velocity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Albatross C_p: 0.440–0.445 Max Power: 22.95KW Stork C_p: 0.384–0.407 Max Power: 21 KW 	[21]
2018	Butterfly Wing	VAWT	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blade twist mechanism using centrifugal force for over-speed control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C_p: 0.415 at TSR = 3.7 Improved twist control at wind speeds >18 m/s 	[22]
2024	Dragonfly Wing	HAWT	Tandem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dragonfly-inspired two-blade turbine derived from CFD simulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C_p: 0.35 at TSR = 3 	[23]

4. Recommendation and Challenges

Based on the research, Maple seeds and Albatross & Stork wings would be the best nature inspired modifications for lower wind speed region like Bangladesh. Both methods proved their ability to enhance power efficiency and increase efficiency. Bangladesh is situated in coastal and rural regions. So, these methods can be both low cost and applicable to horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines. Fig. 2 represents the performance reflection of Table 1.

Among the major challenges, maintenance and lack of technical expertise can be a vital obstacle to implement bio inspired approach in wind turbines. Lack of awareness regarding biomimicry principles presents the primary barrier to its adoption in an infrastructure limited country like Bangladesh [24]. The wind conditions can also be a problem in Bangladesh as there are fluctuations in wind speed. However, by focusing on adoptable methods, Bangladesh can improve its renewable energy infrastructure and ensure more efficient energy production.

Fig. 2. Increase of wind turbine power coefficient by nature inspired methods

5. Conclusion

This study examines different biomimetic approaches and their comparison in increasing the aerodynamic performance of a wind turbine. Eight different nature inspired methods were compared to find out the best modification for a wind turbine. The study started by analyzing several performance affecting factors of a wind turbine such as, wind speed, temperature, number of blades, swept area, blade length and air density. The requirement of performance enhancement leads us towards different nature inspired strategies including Maple seed, Borneo Camphor seed, Fibonacci spiral, Humpback whale flippers, butterfly wings, Albatross and Stork wings, dragonfly wings. Maple seed, Albatross and Stork wings demonstrated their potential of increasing the performance of a wind turbine effectively for Bangladesh perspective. The application of Maple seed geometry in HAWT increase the C_p by almost 59%. The use of Albatross and Stork inspired design showed maximum power up to 22.95 KW and 21 KW respectively, by maintaining a maximum C_p up to 44.5%.

However, nature inspired methods need to be more widely popularized and required further research and development with skilled engineers to overcome the implementation complexities in Bangladesh.

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